

Appendix A

The infrared spectra of selected nanoporous graphene quantum dots shown in Fig. S1 indicate that there are no imaginary frequencies. This means that there are no saddle points and the structures correspond to a minimum on the B3LYP potential energy surface. Thus the considered systems are dynamically stable.

Fig. S1. The Infrared spectra of selected nanoporous graphene quantum dots before and after chemical modification and adsorption of heavy metals.

Appendix B

The results of the ab initio molecular dynamics simulations for the nanoporous graphenes at 500K are shown in Figs. S2 and S3. The trajectories in the figures show that the changes in the total energy and the bond lengths at 500K for 5 femtoseconds is very small, indicating the thermal stability of the considered adsorbents at high temperature.

Fig. S2. The time evolution of the total energy and selected bond lengths of nanoporous graphenes before and after chemical modification at 500K.

Fig. S3. The same as in Fig. S2 but for additional nanoporous graphenes.

Appendix C

Here we present the maximum number of Cd atoms that can be adsorbed by Z120-N-PG, as an example, with moderate adsorption energy, slight deformation, and no metal-metal clusters formation. It is observed that the selected PG can adsorb up to 30 Cd atoms on one side with acceptable adsorption energy and negligible deformation as shown in Fig. S4 (d). Increasing the number to 39 atoms, the metals start forming Cd-Cd clusters due to the small separation between them which significantly deteriorates the adsorption process.

Fig. S4. (a-d) Optimized structure of Z120-N-PG adsorbing different numbers of Cd-atoms on one side. (e) Non-optimized structure showing the Cd-Cd clustering when the number of Cd atoms increased to 39. (f) The optimized structure of Z120-N-PG after adsorbing 26 Cd atoms on both sides.

Appendix D

Fig. S5. presents the second part of complexes, in which the effect of chemical functionalization on the adsorption properties of PG toward Cd, Hg, and Pb. The calculated adsorption energy increases after chemical modification.

Fig. S5. The optimized structures and the adsorption energy of chemically functionalized-PGs after the adsorption of Cd (a-c), Hg (d-f), and Pb (g-i).